

WOMEN EMPLOYEES IN SPINNING MILLS IN NAMAKKAL DISTRICT: A STUDY ON SAFETY ISSUES AND PROVISIONS

Dr. D. KANCHANA

Assistant Professor and HOD, Department of Business Administration, Arignar Anna Government Arts College, Namakkal E-Mail: kanchanad581970@gmail.com

C. HAMSAVENI

Ph.D. Research Scholar, Department of Business Administration, Arignar Anna Government Arts College, Namakkal. E-Mail: hanish8587@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Word safety should be monitored in a sensitive approach, keeping an eye out for differences in how women are exposed to dangers compared to males. The study investigated the safety issues and provisions for women workers in spinning mills in the Namakkal district. The study's research strategy is based on naturalistic observation and surveys, and the findings will be described. According to the results, seventeen big spinning mills employ 383 women. Primary or secondary data have been utilised in the study. The preliminary data were gathered using an interview schedule, while the secondary data are mostly documentary. Most respondents in a simple random sampling come from the primary defined weaker parts of the socioeconomic spectrum. The data in this study were analysed using Garrett's ranking approach. A company's ability to effectively manage its human resource base will positively impact all other aspects of the business. The study indicated that organisations have embraced a safety-first mentality.' On the other hand, workers are not as concerned about safety as they should be. Every stakeholder in a company has a role to play in ensuring employee safety, not just the employer. In this study, the researcher focused on an important subject that necessitated ongoing research to discover new diseases and avoid them.

Keywords: Environmental System, Labour Welfare, Occupational Disease, Safety Issues, Safety Provisions.

INTRODUCTION

Word safety should be monitored in a sensitive approach, keeping an eye out for differences in how women are exposed to dangers compared to males. Participatory, incorporating the workers involved, and assessing the actual work situation are the best ways to deal with sexual orientation sensitive interventions. Executives must take security, well-being, and sexual orientation concerns seriously, and no assumptions should be made about who is in danger from which threats. It is a fundamental obligation.

- Sexist issues should be considered at each stage of the threat assessment process. For example, ask both male and female labourers about their concerns in an organised fashion.
- When "grading" high, medium, or low hazards, be aware of the possibility of an unanticipated sex inclination.

- When eliminating or substituting dangerous substances, make sure that conceptive medical issues are considered.
- Preventive apportionment should cover the two people's assignments.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ergonomic risks like shaky hand apparatuses and pesticide and solvent exposure were among the hazards identified by Loewenson (1998). An estimated ten- to one-hundredfold increase in wound and illness rates has been reported. An increased risk of respiratory and musculoskeletal illnesses, such as asthma and allergies, and physical exhaustion and fatigue, were also identified. Wounds inflicted by instruments were also common.

Briar, C. (2009) studied female workers' health and safety issues. With the burden of home-grown work and its inherent dangers, women are exposed to many potential contributory disease causes. Women's greater propensity to be the primary caregiver in the family makes stress and musculoskeletal disorders more likely. Burnout is more likely for women since they have less time to rest and need to de-stress for more extended periods.

Workers in informal divisions were exposed to physical, ergonomic, chemical, and psychological dangers, according to Ametepheh (2011). Despite this, occupational health and safety operations were confined to the formal area to disregard the informal divisions in the workforce. Workers and managers are aware of occupational and environmental health hazards. Still, the lack of a clear plan and the lack of permanent workplaces discourage representatives from investing in occupational health and safety.

Arif (2011) looked at the workings and problems of the Maharashtra force loom industry. Workers in the force loom sector have access to basic factory amenities. The study concluded that workers' satisfaction is based on their wages and benefits. Many workers were unhappy with the factory's working conditions, such as the amount of dust and vapour generated. The industry has no regard for sanitary conditions, safety measures, or proper lighting and ventilation.

For example, heat, light, clamour, radiation, and chemicals that cause dermatitis and lung ailments are among the physical hazards that industrial workers face, according to Park. K (2011). Bacteria, viral and fungal infections cause about 10% of industry-related accidents; the other 90% are due to mechanical causes, such as moving machinery parts. Workplace stress, anxiety, and depression can lead to psychological problems.

In a case study of Okhla and Noida, Upadhyaya S (2011) investigated private security employees' labour, business, and social security challenges. The study focuses primarily on working hours, salary, leave, and business security. Select safety officers, agencies and bosses were asked to fill out an organised questionnaire.

According to Walt A et al. (2012), pepper mills and spice mills threaten those who work in this area. Spices are derived from various plants, some allergenic and can cause mild to severe systemic reactions. Workers at a spice mill rely primarily on inhalation as a method of

communication. Chronic airway inflammation and obstructive pulmonary illness are strongly associated with stew pepper sensitisation.

According to Abolfazl Ghahramani (2016), occupational health and safety net the implementation of numerous strategies and measures by the company to guard against evolving dangers. Many organisations have implemented OHSAS because of its favourable effect on reducing risks.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study was placed third on the list of leading causes of death by the National Institutes of Occupational Health and Safety (NIOHS). Unquestionably one of the most critical yet under-recognised challenges for workers is the risk of injury and illness from their employment. Employees and employers alike do not seem to take it seriously. There is a lot of legislation to safeguard employees' rights and fitness, but not all of it is implemented, and only a select few profit from it. 8.8% of the workforce is organised. Because of the high unemployment rate, the force is readily available to be exploited. Getting a job is more important than the risks involved. According to a paper on regional strategy, south-East Asian countries' occupational health and safety burdens are still largely unknown. The Bhopal catastrophe in India and the Kader Toy Factory fire in Thailand have exposed severe occupational health issues in Member Countries.

In contrast, the region's employees are subjected to a more excellent range of occupational hazards and dangers, including chemical, physical, and biological hazards, inadequate ergonomic practices, and significant psychosocial stress. As most of the region's states are experiencing significant economic growth, this could amplify existing traditional dangers and introduce new occupational hazards to the area. The WHO's South-East Asia Region has a potential workforce of over 560 million people, making occupational health a significant issue in this region. South Asian industrialisation places a high value on output at the expense of worker well-being and public safety. OSHA and other safety and health regulators are omitted to promote investors' low-cost labour.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To investigate the safety issues and provisions for women employees in spinning mills in Namakkal district.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

There are more textiles produced in India than in any other country globally. A high level of activity in consumer purchases and exports has made India's spinning sector world-class, with the most up-to-date machinery and 30-40 per cent higher productivity than even China's textile-producing business. As a result, Indian spinners can better tolerate the more significant investment costs than their Chinese rivals. The Indian spinning sector has perfected the skill of rapid personnel training in addition to machine productivity. A world-class workforce was created in three months, even though the industry received minimal help from the government in developing its training manuals in most Indian languages.

Given that yarn has been the most critical growth engine for textile exports, it makes sense, with a value increase of 30%. In states where cotton is plentiful, and good incentives are available, investment in this advanced manufacturing sector will rise, especially if policy aberrations are corrected.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

In Namakkal District, data were only gathered from a small number of people who agreed to participate in the study. Other parts of the population or a different location could alter the results. “A lack of data has hindered secondary data collection.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study’s research strategy is based on naturalistic observation and surveys, and the findings will be described. According to the results, 17 big spinning mills employ 383 women. Primary or secondary data have been utilised in the study. The preliminary data were gathered using an interview schedule, while the secondary data are mostly documentary. Most respondents in a simple random sampling come from the primary defined weaker parts of the socioeconomic spectrum. The data in this study were analysed using Garrett’s ranking approach.

SAFETY ISSUES OF THE WOMEN EMPLOYEES IN SPINNING MILLS

Many milling machines are now automated, but not all and not in all countries. Competent employees still operate many devices and may inadvertently injure themselves by snaring their hands and fingers—the breakdown of natural and synthetic fibres in the air during cotton processing results in cotton dust. Chemical insecticides on the cotton and dirt combine to create this dust. If the workers are not protected, they will inhale all of them. Employees who are exposed to it may get serious lung problems. It is common for textile factories to have enormous rooms packed with textile machinery. The noise from the machines is harmful to the ear, especially if it is repeated over an extended period. Manufacturing in textile mills and other facilities is fraught with potential dangers and should be avoided. Concerns about the health and safety of women who work in spinning mills were examined, including the availability of first aid services, health and safety policies, environmental protection measures, and ecological stewardship efforts such as providing access to clean water and conducting regular medical exams. The following table summarises the results of applying Garrett’s ranking system to determine the importance of various concerns.

TABLE 1: SAFETY ISSUES OF THE WOMEN EMPLOYEES IN SPINNING MILLS

S. No	Issues	Total score	Mean Score	Rank
1	First aid facilities or arrangements available in the mill	70478	70.478	1
2	Safety health and environmental manager in the mill	35555	35.555	10
3	Having an awareness of the occupational disease	43718	43.718	7
4	Any awareness of the safety, environmental issues, and labour welfare	39691	39.691	9
5	Protect and contribute to the environmental system	49037	49.037	6
6	Providing purified water facility	56094	56.094	4
7	Medical check-up conducted at the time of recruitment selection	30527	30.527	11
8	Having awareness about personal protective equipment	55759	55.759	5
9	Distribution of preventive measures among workers at the time of emergency	59206	59.206	3
10	Safety instructions displayed on the dangerous machine	66631	66.631	2
11	Ideas to avoid diseases and physical damages	41304	41.304	8

The above table understands issues in spinning mills. The results show that the prime point of women employees in spinning mills is “First-aid facility or arrangements available in the mill,” having a mean score of 70.478, followed by safety instruction displayed on the dangerous machine (66.631). The mean score of the safety issue “Distribution of preventive measures among workers at the time of emergency” is 59.206, and it occupies the third position. The mean score of the safety issues “Providing purified water facility” and “Having awareness about personal protective equipment” are 56.094 and 55.759, with fourth and fifth positions. The sixth mean rank (49.037) given by the women employees working in spinning mills is “Protect and contribute to the environmental system.” Having an awareness of the occupational disease among the women employees in spinning mills was positioned in the

seventh rank with 43.718 points, followed by ideas to avoid infections and physical damage (41.304). The mean score for the safety issues “Any awareness towards the environmental safety issues and labour welfare” and “Safety health and environmental manager in the mill” are 36.691 and 35.555, with ninth and tenth positions. The last part (eleven) was occupied by the issue “Medical check-up conducted during recruitment selection” with 30.527 points. Hence, the first aid facility or arrangements available in the spinning mill was the primary safety issue recommended by the women employees.

AVAILABILITY OF SAFETY PROVISIONS IN SPINNING MILLS

Efficiencies in spinning mills are rising as modern technologies expand the types of yarns they can create. However, the desire to improve female employees’ health, safety, and well-being must also guide these changes. These advances must be implemented in older businesses that are only marginally financially viable and unwilling to make the necessary investments and in growing areas eager to create new sectors even at the expense of women employees’ health and safety. Women employees can still be educated and trained to minimise their hazards, even in these challenging conditions. Considering these conditions, safety provisions for women workers in spinning mills were examined, including the ego problem, cultural differences with migrants, low approachability, difficulty extracting work from subordinates, regular conflict, and lack of trust. The following table reveals all the pertinent information.

TABLE 2: AVAILABILITY OF SAFETY PROVISIONS IN SPINNING MILLS

S. No.	Provision	Total score	Mean Score	Rank
1	Gloves	38327	38.327	3
2	Masks	64974	64.974	1
3	Earmuffs	61194	61.194	2
4	Goggles overall	35505	35.505	4

The above table shows the safety provision available in spinning mills. Provision of masks was placed in the first rank with a mean score of 61.194. Another safety provision, “Earmuffs,” was earmarked in the second place by the sample of women employees working in spinning mills with a mean value of 61.194. The mean score of the safety provision “Gloves” is 38.327, which occupied the third position. The final fourth mean rank (35.505) of women employees working in the spinning mill is “Goggles overall.” Hence, it was found that the provision of masks was placed in the first rank among the various safety provision highlighted by the sample women employees in spinning mills.

SUGGESTIONS

All Industrial Health & Safety Services facets require a permanent and active research wing to function correctly. Traditional diseases like Byssinosis and silicosis and occupational disorders focus on research centres like the National Institute of Occupational Health (NIOH).

It is possible to gain fresh insights and act if you look at experience studies from the right angle. Accidents, occupational diseases, and problems with mental health care should be documented, and the methods are taken to address them.

Occupation-related illness should always be examined critically. As a result, new facts may be discovered, and new measures will be developed.

The nature of the industry is rapidly changing due to rising industrialisation. Because of the industry's rapid evolution, modern technologies may bring more significant unknown dangers and diseases of their creation. Only through a watchful research wing can they deal with these challenges in industrial safety & health services.

CONCLUSION

A company's ability to effectively manage its human resource base will positively impact all other aspects of the business. The study indicated that organisations have embraced a safety-first mentality.' On the other hand, workers are not as concerned about safety as they should be. Every stakeholder in a company has a role to play in ensuring employee safety, not just the employer. In this study, the researcher focused on an important subject that necessitated ongoing research to discover new diseases and avoid them.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Abolfazl Ghahramani (2016) An investigation of safety climate in OHSAS 18001certified and non-certified organisations, *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Ergonomics*, 22:3, 414-421, DOI: 10.1080/10803548.2016.1155803

Ometepe, R .S. (2011). The occupational health and safety of the informal services sector in the Sekondi-Takoradi metropolitan area. Available at: http://dspace.knust.edu.gh:8080/jspui/bitstream/123456789/215811/RejoiceSelorm_Ametepeh.pdf Accessed 15/12/11.

Arif. A. T. D.V. (2011, June). An analytical study of the function and the problems of the power loom industry in Maharashtra with particular reference to Malegaon Dist Nashik. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance*, 2 (3), 1-10.

Briar, C. (2009) "A safe job? Health and safety risks in women's work", in C. Briar (ed.) *Hidden health hazards in women's work*, Wellington: Dunmore Publishing.

Jeebhay, M.F.; Van der Walt, A. Work-related allergy and asthma to inhaled spices-a review: ALLSA Research Awards report-allergies in the workplace. *Curr. Allergy Clin. Immunol.* 2010, 23, 186–192, 2012.

Loewenson, R.H.(1998). Health impact of occupational risks in the informal sector in Zimbabwe. *International Journal of occupational and environmental health*, 4(4), 264274.